

SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONSEQUENCES OCCURRED AMONG THE TRIBAL BENEFICIARIES AS A RESULT OF THE WADI PROJECT IN THE GOALPARA DISTRICT SPECIAL REFERENCE TO LAKHIPUR BLOCK ASSAM

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Abstract

The Wadi project focuses on the development of orchards (recognized locally as Wadi), particularly on degraded lands. Through this program, tribal people cultivate mangoes, cashews, guavas, custard apples, alans, lemons, sapota, and drumsticks. The scope of the present study was to explore the socio-economic implications of such a project for its beneficiaries as a result of the WADI. The study was conducted in Lakhipur block in the Goalpara district. The list of all WADI tribal beneficiaries was collected from the Lakhipur block office, Po-Lakhipur, District-Goalpara, Assam. For this investigation, a proportionate random sampling method was employed to select 110 tribal beneficiaries from the 14 villages spread across four talukas in the Lakhipur block of Goalpara district. The structured schedule was developed to measure the socioeconomic consequences of the Wadi project on tribal beneficiaries. Analyses found that these had medium to high significance, with variables such as education, land holding, occupation, income, source of information, social participation and risk orientation among those observed to have an effect. It was also found that economic motivation, scientific orientation, extension contact, and aspirations had significantly affected outcomes. Moreover, socio-economic consequences were associated with cohesiveness, management orientation, communication skills, and proximity to the market. Finally farming experience, innovativeness, and training acquired were significant factors in determining outcomes.

Keywords: Socio-Economic, Consequences, Tribal People, Beneficiaries, WADI Project.

INTRODUCTION

The Wadi project mainly involves the development of orchards (locally known as Wadi) on degraded lands. Mango, Cashew, Guava, Custard apple, Aonla, Lemon, Sapota, and Drumstick are the major fruit crops that are cultivated by the tribal through the WADI project. Wadi is a comprehensive project for improving the living standards and socio-economic conditions of tribal families in remote areas.

The consequence refers to the alteration that takes place either in an individual or a social system due to the acceptance or rejection of an innovative idea. The study defines it as the changes that happened to tribal beneficiaries concerning socio-economic aspects after adopting components of Wadi project.

These comprise thirteen primary elements such as transformation in land usage pattern, Agri-Horti-forestry production, annual income, consumption of farm inputs, modern technology-based farm machinery, etc.

A change in household items, change in saving and investment, change in food habits, change in clothing, change in housing, change in social status, change in self-sufficiency, and change in social relationships were all considered as the consequences of the Wadi project.

THE OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To know the because of the Wadi project, socioeconomic consequences occurred among tribal beneficiaries.
2. To the analysis of how the Wadi project impacts tribal beneficiaries on a socioeconomic level
3. The purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between the profile of tribal beneficiaries and their socioeconomic status.

METHODOLOGY

This study examined the socioeconomic consequences of the Wadi project among beneficiaries. The study was conducted in Lakhipur block, Goalpara Because the WADI project was started in this block with a maximum number of beneficiaries of the project.

A list of all tribal beneficiaries of the WADI project was collected from the Lakhipur Development block, Dist. Goalpara, Assam. The random sampling method was used for the selection of 110 tribal beneficiaries from the 14 villages of 4 taluka for the present investigation. To measure socioeconomic consequences, a structured schedule was developed.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Socioeconomic consequences occurred among tribal beneficiaries.

A t-test was used to determine the difference in 13 aspects by obtaining the mean scores. The data regarding these 13 aspects are provided in Table 1.

Table 1: Aspect wise socio-economic consequences occurred because of WADI Project N=110

Sl. No	Aspects	Mean Score		Mean Difference	"t" Value
		Before Project	After Project		
1	Change In land Pattern	1.24	1.35	0.09	4.453**
2	Change in Agri-Horti-Forestry production	1.876	2.22	0.52	12.455**
3	Changes in Annual Income (Rs)	35002.7	53679	20766.77	23.3753**
4	Change in Modern Technologies	4.6788	5.233	0.86	15.455**
5	Change in Household items	5.3453	6.11	0.9123	17.6786**
6	Change in food habit	4.5666	5.566	0.6623	7.654**
7	Change in Housing	2.5877	2.98	0.345	8.564**
8	Change in Social Status	4.545	4.78	0.432	7.345**
9	Change in Self-sufficiency	2.7889	3.344	0.6521	16.456**
10	Change in social relationship	5.5677	6.456	1.1345	10.8765**
Overall Consequences		36.5423	47.046	10.5322	27.876**

*Significant at 5 %

** Significant at 1%

What's more, a great transformation happened in the event of Changes in land pattern (4.453**), change in Agri-Horti-forestry production (12.455**), Change in Annual Income (23.3753**), Changes in Modern Technology based on farm machinery and implements (15.455**), Change in the household (17.678**), Followed by changes in food habit (7.654**), Changes in housing facilities (8.5640**), Followed by Change in Social status (7.345**), Change in Self-sufficiency (16.456**), and followed by a change in a social relationship (10.8765**). And the overall socio-economic consequences (27.876**).

The Wadi project impacts tribal beneficiaries on a socioeconomic level.

Table 2: Distribution of tribal beneficiaries based on their socioeconomic status. N=110

Sl. No	Impacts tribal beneficiaries on a socioeconomic level	Frequency	Percent%
1	The low extent of Socioeconomic consequence	23	21
2	Medium impact of socioeconomic consequences	59	53
3	The high impact of socioeconomic consequences	28	26

(Mean =45.34 and SD=5.21)

According to the table, 53% percent of tribal beneficiaries experienced medium socioeconomic consequences because of the Wadi project, followed by 26%percent with high and 21% with low consequences.

The relationship between the profile of tribal beneficiaries and their socioeconomic status.

Based on the data in table 3, education (0.435**), Land Holding (00.14**), Occupation (0.41**)Annual Income(0.621**), Source of Information(0.373**), and Social participation (0.353**), followed by risk orientation(0.42**), economic motivation (0.4321**), scientific orientation(0.3912**), extension contract (0.365**), followed by aspiration(0.345**), cohesiveness (0.523**), Management orientation (0.3665**), communication skill (0.345**), distance from the market (0.351**) fund highly significant associated With socio-economic

consequences occurred among tribal beneficiaries of WADI Project.

Further, the farming experience (0.176*) followed by innovativeness (0.1346*), followed by training acquired (0.112*) among tribal beneficiaries, were significantly associated with the socio-economic consequences of the Wadi project.

The age (-0.367**) was highly negative and significantly associated with the socio-economic consequences impact among the tribal beneficiaries as a result of the WADI Project. On the other hand, Family size (0.0056^{NS}) was a non-significant association with the socio-economic consequences that occurred among tribal beneficiaries because of the WADI Project.

Table 3: Investigates the relationship between the profile of tribal beneficiaries and their socioeconomic status. N=110

Sl. No	Independent Variable	Socio-economic Consequences ("r" Value)
X ₁	Age	-0.367**
X ₂	Education	0.435**
X ₃	Family Size	0.0056 ^{NS}
X ₄	Land Holding	0.41**
X ₅	Farming Experience	0.176*
X ₆	Occupation	0.41**
X ₇	Annual income	0.4621**
X ₈	Source of Information	0.373**
X ₉	Social participation	0.353**
X ₁₀	Risk orientation	0.42**
X ₁₁	Economic motivation	0.4321**
X ₁₂	Scientific Orientation	0.3912**
X ₁₃	Extension contacts	0.365**
X ₁₄	Innovativeness	0.1356*
X ₁₅	Training acquired	0.112*
X ₁₆	Aspiration	0.345**
X ₁₇	Cohesiveness	0.523**
X ₁₈	Management orientation	0.3765**
X ₁₉	Communication Skill	0.345**
X ₂₀	Distance from market	0.351**

CONCLUSION

A major shift was seen in land use, Agri-Horti-forestry production, annual income, and the consumption of farm inputs. This was accompanied by a transformation in modern technology-based farm machinery, household items, savings and investments, diet, clothing styles, housing standards, social status, and self-sufficiency. These sweeping changes also brought about profound socio-economic consequences. It was found to be highly significant. The tribal beneficiaries possessed medium to high socioeconomic consequences occurred among beneficiaries as a result of Wadi project.

he education, land holding, occupation, annual income, source of information, social participation, risk orientation, economic motivation, scientific orientation, extension contact,

and aspiration; cohesiveness; management orientation; communication skill and distance from the market were all found to be significantly associated with the socio-economic consequences experienced by tribal beneficiaries as a result of the Wadi project. Moreover, farming experience, innovativeness and training acquired were also shown to have an impact on these effects. It was found to be highly significant. The tribal beneficiaries possessed medium to high socioeconomic consequences.

Reference

- 1) Darandale, A. A. (2015). Consequential Assessment of the Farmers about Adoption of Recommended Practices of Major Crops in South Gujarat. Ph.D. thesis (unpublished) submitted to N.A.U., Navsari, Gujarat.
- 2) Vinaya Kumar, H. M., Yashodhara.B., Preethi and Govinda Gowda, V. (2015). Impact of Community Based Tank Management Project on Socio-Economic Status and Crop Productivity of Beneficiary Farmers in Tumkur District of Karnataka State. *Trends in Biosciences*. 8(9): 2289-2295
- 3) Matwa, J. (2012). Consequences of ATMA project on maize growers. M.Sc. (Agri.) thesis (unpublished) submitted to A.A.U., Anand, Gujarat.
- 4) Vinaya Kumar, H. M., Biradar, G. S., Nagaraj, and Govinda Gowda, V. (2013). Impact of Community Based Tank Management Project on Socio-Economic Status of Beneficiary Farmers. *Environment and Ecology*. 31 (2A): 620-625.
- 5) Pandya, S. P., Prajapati, M. R. and Patel, K. S. (2016). Relationship between characteristics of the farmers with change in socio economic impact as a result of participating in Krushi Mahostav. *Guj. J. Extn. Edu.*, 27 (2): 212-214
- 6) Ninama, M. D., Patel, J.B. and Raghuvansh, S.K. (2016). Relationship between impact of check dam on sociotechno-economic status of tribal farmers. *Guj. J. Extn. Edu.*, 27 (2) : 204-205
- 7) Vinaya Kumar, H. M., Shivamurthy, M., Govinda Gowda, V. and Biradar, G. S. (2017). Assessing decision-making and economic performance of farmers to manage climate-induced crisis in Coastal Karnataka (India). *Climatic Change*. Springer, May 2017, 142 (1):43– 153. doi:10.1007/s10584-017-1928-x